

Doing Good Led by the Good Spirit, Thinking with the Church

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Pope Francis’s discourse to the members of the General Congregation (GC) 36 has two broad sections. The first introductory section draws our attention to the original inspiration of St. Ignatius and his first companions, in other words, to the charismatic sources of the Institute of the Society of Jesus. Pope Francis identifies “drawing greater fruit” as the practical criterion of discernment of Ignatius and his first companions in order to “help souls” (*ayudar a las almas*, *Autob* 45). Ignatius understood himself as a pilgrim, and wanted the Society to be the same. Jerome Nadal, one of the early companions of Ignatius used to say that “for the Society the whole world is our home” (M Nadal V 364-365). A pilgrim is one who keeps moving forward. In the second section of his discourse, Pope Francis defines three ways of keeping the Ignatian legacy alive by “moving forward ... in the service of God and seeking greater good”. We move ahead by, *i*) Asking insistently for consolation, *ii*) Letting ourselves be moved by our Lord placed on the cross and *iii*) Doing good led by the good spirit, thinking with the Church. In this article we will try understand the last of the three ways of moving forward.

This third subtitle makes the reference to two sets of rules or guidelines given in the book of the *Spiritual Exercises*: *i*) *Rules to aid us toward perceiving and then understanding, at least to some extent, the various motions which are caused in the soul; the good motions that they may be received, and the bad that*

they may be rejected (SpEx [313-327]). ii) To have the genuine attitude which we ought to maintain in the Church Militant, we should observe the following rules (SpEx [352-370]). The first set of rules are better known as “Rules of the Discernment of Spirits” and the second set as “Rules for Thinking with the Church” or *Sentire cum ecclesia* as designated in the official Vulgate text of the *Exercises* by Andrea Frusio.

The Pope speaks of doing good led by the Good Spirit. This implies that one could do good led by the Bad Spirit. To understand this dynamism, one needs to understand what Ignatius means by Discernment of Spirits. The title of the Rules for Discernment concisely explains what discernment is. There are two types of movements operative in the human heart. One type caused by the Good Spirit or the Spirit of God and the other by the Bad Spirit or the spirit of the Evil One. The Good Spirit causes spiritual consolation in the human heart, i.e., joy and increase of theological virtues of faith, hope and love. This genuine consolation leads the person to do good. The Ignatian guidelines explain to us that when a person advances in spiritual life, the Evil One tries subtle strategies by taking the guise of Good Spirit in order to lead the person away from God. The Evil Spirit produces in the human heart effects that are similar to the ones produced by the Good Spirit. We call it false consolation. The person here may be led to do good, but this good is only apparent good, for the ultimate intention of the Evil One is not good.

A couple of examples will help us understand this better. Let us take a novice who follows the time-table to perfection, spends long hours in the chapel etc. These acts are good in themselves. But, the question to be asked here is, what moves her to these good actions? If she is seeking self-aggrandisement and to impress her novice mistress, she is being moved by the Evil Spirit who has produced false consolation in her. Thus she is doing good led by the Evil Spirit. Or take for example a politician who, before the elections does a lot of good work in his constituency. What is moving him to do the good work? Is

it genuine wellbeing of the people or desire for power? He could be doing the good work merely for acquiring power. That would be doing the good led by the Evil Spirit.

“It’s not enough to think, do or organise the good , but do it of the Good Spirit”, says the Pope. One has to pause to ask oneself before acting, “which spirit is guiding me?” Pope Francis refers to Peter Faber saying that, “in many things, those who wanted to reform the Church were right, but that God did not want to correct it through their means”. Faber was writing that from his experience of working with the Protestants in Germany. He realised that, though the ideals for which the Protestants were fighting were good in themselves, the means they took to achieve them were not inspired by the Good Spirit. The Good Spirit unites. The Evil Spirit divides. The Rules for Thinking with the Church had the concern of preserving the unity of the Church. The Protestants broke away from the Church because they lacked obedience to the authority of the Church. And why should one obey the dictates of the Church? In the thirteenth Rule Ignatius gives his rationale, “we believe that between Christ our Lord, the Bridegroom, and the Church, his Spouse, there is the one same Spirit who governs and guides us for the salvation of our souls” (*SpEx* [365]). In his time Ignatius “acted against” anti-ecclesial spirit and today the Pope is inviting us to do the same. At the same time he adds a word of caution. He calls us not be clericalists but to be ecclesiastics, i.e., to be women and men of discernment who do good inspired by the Good Spirit.

We live in a world full of conflicts and contexts of sin abound. The pope invites us to be men and women of the Church in this context without losing peace and joy. How can one be equanimous in the present context of India where the Indian Church faces persecution? Pope Francis says, “Where the contradiction was very clear, Ignatius used to advise to recollect oneself, before talking or acting, in order to work in the Good Spirit”. This brings to my mind the bewilderment of Arjuna in the Kurukṣetra. Kṛṣṇa’s advice to him according to Gīta 2: 47 is

of *niṣkāmakarma* - disinterested action. We may not agree with the *dharma* (will of God in a broad sense) determined by birth, but once one has discerned the will of God he or she must act without desiring the fruit of the action, which depends entirely on God. The consequence of disinterested action could well be carrying the cross as the Pope remarks, but interiorising the attitude of *niṣkāmakarma* could become a source of equanimity.

The *Kenosis* of God made incarnation possible. Similarly, our own self-emptying will make us servants, ready to be sent - *apostles*, in the midst of peoples and cultures and help them “become the Church”.

Towards the end of this reflection Pope Francis links the spirit of discernment with the inculturation of the gospel and becoming all things to all people. That is because discernment implies listening (to the Spirit) and listening implies self-emptying. One who is full of oneself

does not know how to listen. One needs to set aside one’s prejudices (Cf. *SpEx* [353]), both good and bad, in order to listen effectively. God’s project of inculturation was incarnation. The *Kenosis* of God made incarnation possible. Similarly, our own self-emptying will make us servants, ready to be sent - *apostles*, in the midst of peoples and cultures and help them “become the Church”.

An audience with the Pope is a traditional practice during the GCs. The delegates used to go to meet the Pope. This time, the Pope himself came to meet the delegates, which created history. The delegates were, in fact, expecting a mission that the Pope would assign to them. But the Pope did not tell us Jesuits what we should *do* but rather told us *to* be men of discernment!